

THE READING EXPERIENCE LEADING TO THE LOGICAL LEARNING PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

This article addresses the theme of educational cognitive development, highlighting that the reading experience is a decisive factor in the conduct of logical learning. Its scientific relevance lies in the fact that it addresses a situation in which experience is directly responsible for promoting learning, determining the directions and essential conditions for it, providing a way to understand how children, in their initial stages of building their intellect, gradually become aware of written symbolic forms and their oral expression, through a process of reciprocity and simultaneity. It is a bibliographical research, based on the authors' pedagogical practice, with regard to the teaching of reading, literacy and linguistic literacy. Learning to read is the first step towards achieving reading mastery and this should be taken as a careful and well-planned process, because when demanding fluency from a child in reading and, in the same way, in writing, this can create a block in their creative capacity, limited by their mental age and which is not within the reach of meeting the expectations set by teachers. What we can conclude is that as you master the reading technique, through the experience of the act of reading, you will increase your vocabulary and lexical field.

Keywords: Reading. Reading experience. Literacy. Linguistic literacy. Logical learning.

INTRODUCTION

The teaching of Portuguese and reading in basic education has been the center of discussion about the need to add quality to learning processes. In elementary education, the

focus of discussion, with regard to school failure, has been on the issue reading. It is known that Brazilian repetition rates in the initial grades are unacceptable and, even in much poorer countries, such results are directly linked to the difficulties that schools have in teaching reading. This difficulty is clearly expressed in the two sides, where most repetitions are concentrated; at the end of the first grade (or even the first two) and in the sixth year of Elementary School.

In the first case, due to teachers' difficulty in teaching students to read and write; in the second case, due to their inability to ensure effective use of language, a condition for students to continue progressing until at least the end of the 9th grade; however, this decline in learning and mastery of reading does not stop there, considering that many students reach higher education with difficulties in interpreting and understanding texts proposed for reading and in organizing ideas. This evidence of failure in teaching and learning to read points to the need to restructure the teaching of the Portuguese language, with the aim of finding ways to truly ensure mastery of reading in the teaching-learning process.

Mastery of language is closely related to the possibility of full social participation; considering that it is through language that man communicates, has access to information, expresses and defends points of view, shares or constructs world biases, and produces knowledge.

An educational project committed to social and cultural development assigns the school the role and responsibility of guaranteeing all students access to the linguistic knowledge necessary for learning and mastering reading. Many teachers argue that teaching them is difficult to implement, because

Reading is not seen by students as a source that provides access to information, world knowledge and intellectual growth. [*Therefore*], we are faced with students who have difficulty using standard language, do not know how to organize their own thoughts, only like to read what interests them and often forget the purpose of reading and read quickly, without paying attention, trying to get to the end of the book as quickly as possible (SILVA, 2013, p. 4).

If this is the problem that is posed as a challenge to both teaching and learning to read, we must look more deeply into the elements that led to this *sui generis condition*. Learning is something that suggests experience, being interpreted as a result of it and not something that happens randomly and in a way that is alien to the individual and their praxis.

Therefore, it is necessary to bring the practice of reading closer to the teaching of reading. How the teacher will do this is a question that must be thought out and executed, taking

care to prepare the records and study them exhaustively until a methodology is developed that proves to be efficient; that meets the desires of teachers and apprentices.

READING AND LANGUAGE TEACHING IN NATIONAL CURRICULAR PARAMETERS

The National Curricular Parameters (PCN's) have been showing an objective way of how to proceed in teaching practices, so that education professionals *review* their methodologies and rethink their praxis. Thus, it is possible to think of the Portuguese language as a fundamental need for the development of the student as a starting point for expanding their basic knowledge, starting from the first stage, *the first letters* .

It is necessary for the student to know how to use the vernacular language and its linguistic resources, with respect and autonomy. According to what is foreseen in the duration of a school year, the teacher must teach the alphabetic writing system (phonographic correspondence) and orthographic conversions of Portuguese, which guarantees the student the possibility of reading and writing by himself, a condition for him to move on to the second stage, which is literacy, the study of the language itself.

In this regard, it is necessary to state that “the National Curricular Parameters (PCN), by recognizing the complexity of educational practice, seek to assist the teacher in his task of assuming, as a professional, the place that is his due due to his responsibility and importance in the process of training the Brazilian people” (BRASIL, 1997, p. 9).

The acquisition of alphabetic writing does not guarantee that students will be able to understand and produce texts in written language. This learning requires systematic pedagogical work, which is revealed through strict experience, that is, students must be induced to experience their potential through written production, be it short stories, poems, parodies, prose, cartoons.

Cagliari (1990) argues that,

The child, evidently, did not enter the world of language in the same way that an adult begins to learn a foreign language. He was exposed to the linguistic world that surrounds him and in it he traced his own path, creating what he was allowed to do with language. In this process, he allows for an evolution that is not always simple, not always logical, but always consistent with his way of being and existing in the world (CAGLIARI, 1990, p. 17).

The completion of students' activities is the result of the work of the teacher and the children. The teacher is the guide and the stimulator of activities, who must clearly articulate

knowledge and reality; thereby producing a praxis, a relationship of reciprocity and simultaneity between theory and practice. But how can the school be brought closer to the students' daily lives? First of all, oral language must be worked on, which is the externalization of thought and experiences through names, which are transformed into symbolic references.

Students should be encouraged to speak without fear of the linguistic variant they use, considering that this reflects their own existential and social background. The most important thing is for them to speak, to explain and to explain their experiences, because in this way they will be encouraged to use the normative and formal standard of the language as a pedagogical exercise and not as a criterion for judgment. Furthermore, the distinction between oral and written language should be very clear.

It is important for the teacher to consider some essential aspects in developing the student's reading and writing skills. Ensuring that the student has the interest that will awaken the motivation for learning, leading him to observe, think, imagine, create, see the world with different eyes, eyes of sensitivity, feeling the beauty of ordinary things and nature, appreciating music, valuing drawing, assembly, origami, modeling, and collage. Therefore, it is necessary to read poems to stimulate and develop the child's sensitivity, which makes him feel and act. It is also important for the teacher to tell and read stories so that the children can dramatize, perform oral interpretations, discuss, etc.

Writing is connected to the act of reading. The teacher should work on reading with the aim of encouraging the child to write. This way, the student will have material combined with their prior knowledge for their creations, since no one creates something from nothing. Reading different texts will put the child in contact with different approaches, world views and styles.

ABOUT THE READING EXPERIENCE

The practice of reading is indisputable in two dimensions: the first is reading as a process of accessing and learning knowledge of symbols, starting with literacy. The second is reading as an act of understanding texts for the purpose of leisure, pleasure, learning more, curiosity, and allowing the imagination to go further.

Reading must be meaningful, arouse interest, and have a message that captures the attention of readers of any age, but especially children who are trying to develop a taste for reading. In this way, communication has its own specific language and reaches individuals in a specific way.

Written communication, which we come into contact with through reading, involves us globally and, therefore, can cause broad intellectual development in us, highlighting that this must occur through good examples of readers. Hence the importance of reading aloud by the teacher, “because it is a process of construction and reconstruction of meanings in relation to what is seen, heard, felt and thought...” (KLEIMAN, 2007, p. 106)

Reading does not stop when the child learns to unite different symbols, creating connections, so that, forming a word, which forms a sentence, which forms a text; it is much more than this; for this reason, the child, when entering the world of reading, must respect the reading of the world in which he or she is inserted and know it so that the educator can transform and guide this child towards a much broader reading, without limits and without barriers.

Children must learn and develop skills that broaden and improve their linguistic experience, whether in reading, writing or speaking. In order to develop these skills, the teacher must present a dynamic work proposal, in which the student is constantly asked to participate – in writing and orally – in an intense and creative way.

To this end, situations involving real use of the Portuguese language can be simulated, enabling relationships with the world and the student's existential condition. In addition, activities should seek to expand the student's knowledge through integration with other disciplines and with their world so that they can develop reflection and argumentation on issues that reveal themselves as problematic conditions in society.

Students must develop the ability to listen to others and articulate their ideas with autonomy and clarity, both in written and oral expression, as well as becoming proficient readers. In the years after literacy, they must acquire more complex linguistic forms, articulating their ideas better and better, reading with greater autonomy and proficiency, positioning themselves in relation to values conveyed by texts, as well as learning grammatical notions.

It is up to the teacher, using the various resources offered for the development of the student, to maintain a constant dialogue with them that guarantees rewarding results. This means that the student needs to learn to select what he hears and reads, and also to know how to understand different versions that are written in the texts. As the student develops, it is necessary for him to learn to interpret from his analytical perspective and from that of the author. Therefore, understanding the concept of reading is fundamental.

Although there are different meanings, reading assumes the meaning evidenced in what it expresses. What is intended, however, in this case, is to understand reading as pleasure, leisure and a means of learning what is written and which expresses knowledge. In a sense of learning to read, it can be said that it is one of the pertinent parts of the literacy process and of learning

a language. Thus, it can be said that the child reads to learn, to develop intellectually, and to understand what is made available to him. In this case, the sense of autonomy gained by the individual becomes evident, who no longer needs others to read to him the stories that are told in books.

This is a radical cultural shift; in the past, it would have been honorable to have someone tell wonderful stories to others; today, reading them alone in silence is an attitude of power and *status quo*. How much this represents a positive development is a matter for debate; but it is not the subject of argument here; what stands out is the possibility that reading itself gives the reader to explore, at his or her own leisure, the elements that the writers have compiled in their works, expanding the imaginative potential and curiosity of children, young people and adults.

TYPES OF SCHOOL READING

From the moment a human being is born and comes into contact with the world, with other individuals, with reality, he or she begins to practice various forms of reading; and reading becomes part of the moments of life. By observing a baby from birth, one can better understand this process. In the first months of life, the baby begins to decipher code signals, observing the movement of people's lips, voices, images, touches, colors, sounds. And he or she expresses this through crying, improving himself or herself, so that he or she is constantly reading the world and communicating with it, through its conditions, initially instinctively and soon learned through responses to its needs.

A child's childhood is a fantastic, living scenario, full of beautiful images; it is translated into countless texts not written in codes, letters or words. The act of reading is also about relating objects, facts, phenomena and actions. And learning to read, to write and to become literate is, above all, learning to interpret one's own existence in a dynamic relationship. Thus, when a child goes to school to learn to read and write, he or she takes with him or her a wealth of individual reading material, which expresses his or her particular way of seeing and interpreting the world.

The reading process creates a situation in which it seems that the reader is an alienated being and, in the conception of Rubem Alves (1933-2014),

The alienated person is a person who is outside of himself, walking in a world that is not his own; it belongs to someone else. But that is precisely what reading does. To read, one must 'stop my world'; if the world that is my own is not 'turned off', I will not be able to enter the world that is in the book. I

open the book. I turn off my world. I begin reading. I enter a world that is not mine; it belongs to someone else... (ALVES, 1999, p. 57).

Reading, in conceptual terms, is part of the literacy process; it is crucial in an individual's life, as it allows them to interpret their own horizons and objectives. Without this collaboration, it becomes difficult to understand it as an indispensable element for intellectual development and learning, because isolated from a broader context, what we have is the decoding of symbols devoid of any practical effect, that is, everything that is created and recreated ends up being interpreted as something that exists in and of itself, without a meaning to be deciphered, after being extensively analyzed and interpreted, whether individually or in collaboration with others.

Reading is an important mechanism for the appropriation of learning. Scholars, researchers and educators unanimously recognize the great importance and also the necessity of reading for the intellectual development of the individual. It provides important subsidies for communication, both in writing and orally. Through the practice of reading,

Children are immersed in a wonderful world of fairy tales from a very young age, before they start school. Through them, before beginning to enter the universe of the written word, children enjoy the freedom typical of oral language, in which the same story can be retold in different ways (CAVALCANTI, 1997, p. 12).

Knowing the types of reading makes it easier to get involved in other types of values of the act of reading. It is necessary to consider some essential aspect such as those involving the importance of reading, which, however, should be placed as an element that does not become so superior to the point of preventing better performance at a general level. Reading should not be presented as a deification as if it were the only reason to learn and develop intellectually. Knowledge is needed to determine your own reading pace. In order to understand and comprehend what you read, it is important to review and reread as many times as necessary.

The reading process is and should be marked by the dynamism between the didactic action of reading and the practical action of executing it exhaustively, seeking to master intonation, phonetics, canonical terms of the vernacular language, neologisms, semantics and spelling of words. Thus, there is a whole set of actions to be undertaken in the technical acquisition of reading, which, once mastered, leads to fluency. What we seek to achieve, with all these actions, is the conquest of the ability to read any text, from the simplest to the classics of literature that are products of different eras from the one we are experiencing.

Understanding what this domain is, in terms of learning, is what allows the student to have the exact notion that he or she already knows how to read fluently, and can move on to

other ways of applying the knowledge acquired and exploring other domains, going from reading to analysis until reaching the field of interpretation and from there to synthesis. At the same time, the student seeks out authors with a greater degree of interpretative difficulty to submit their comprehension criteria until they become so good at their reading practice that it becomes a praxis.

READING TYPES

Since reading is an activity that produces meaning, it cannot be defined in relation to the reader without first knowing their level of intellectual and reading development. Some methods used for reading stand out and should be conducted based on pedagogical planning:

- ✓ **Silent reading:** After a certain level of mastery of alphabetic writing, it is important to always encourage this practice, as this individual contact between text and reader is essential for understanding the text when the reader's skills and reading strategies are already broad and capable of being mastered. It is important to clarify that reasoning becomes faster in this type of reading; therefore, it should be encouraged based on other results linked to the student's cognitive development; not as a mere practice of the act of reading.
- ✓ **Reading aloud:** Every reading aloud proposal must make sense within the activity in which it is included, and the student must always be able to read the text silently, in advance – once or several times. The teacher needs to guide the development of oral skills and fluency in reading; therefore, he/she needs to listen to the students in their dynamics and conditions of mastery of reading and oral expression, teaching them the procedures of voice intonation, breathing (exhalation and inhalation), verbal and linguistic knowledge of words.
- ✓ **Dramatized reading:** Encounter between verbal and non-verbal expression in the construction of the meaning of a text. Contribute to the student's disinhibition to express their feelings; for the development of body intelligence.
- ✓ **Guided reading:** Ask, for example, the student to read the passage they liked the most, the one that moved them the most, the one that conveyed a certain idea, etc.
- ✓ **Interrupted reading:** This involves interrupting the reading to ask questions about the ideas and characteristics of the discourse presented so far. This is an important practice, especially when reading a reasonably long text.
 - ✓ **Collaborative reading:** Activity in which the teacher reads a text with the class and, during the reading, questions the students about the linguistic clues that allow them to

attribute certain meanings. In addition to orally exploring reading procedures, linguistic and textual knowledge, this practice awakens the pleasure of listening to texts and curiosity.

When teachers are able to guide their students through all these paths of reading, there is progress in understanding what reading practice is, with a view to empirical improvement and in the way experiences are felt and understood. Each text read brings the student closer to the condition of an actor in the process, not a passive being who reads and, in the end, does not even know what he has read, let alone has any understanding and is able to perform levels of interpretation of the subjects covered.

Reading introduces individuals to the existence of other situations similar to the one they are facing and how the participants managed to overcome the challenges that life posed. When the author writes his work, he develops his thesis, bringing his thoughts to life, expressing what he thinks about mechanisms for solving the problems of his time. All of the student's efforts in reading are about trying to find a way, an efficient method to overcome the difficulties that are posed and that, at times, seem insoluble. Therefore, it is the experience acquired through reading that will provide this gain in his journey of transformation. Could this happen through storytelling? Of course it would; but, it would always be under the value judgment of someone else, in which it would be a third party, when in the practice of reading one finds oneself in front of the author, being able to seek to retrace the steps followed by him using, for this purpose, other sciences, such as Anthropology, Sociology, Psychology and Philosophy, recreating the space and time in which this author found himself immersed, creating logical comparisons with his own time, becoming able to interpret him with the maximum clarity and objectivity that his knowledge allows.

It is always necessary to clarify that reading, in itself, does not make an individual intelligent or creative; it is its application to thought and to a hard perspective of analysis of phenomena, both tangible and intangible, that allows one to increasingly broaden one's horizons about things, individuals and the world. Each type of reading will promote a certain field of knowledge and a speed of reasoning, and it is mandatory that one goes through all of them until reaching the level of excellence and, once having reached this point, one knows how to interpret learning situations from the perspective of other authors, academics and scientists in the areas one intends to study.

In order to be able to carry out all the types of reading presented, it is necessary to develop a methodological study plan that takes into account the age of the students, their ability to analyze and interpret texts, vocabulary index, knowledge of thought structures, and their

interest in the subject. It is common to advance the proposal for teaching reading by offering texts that are beyond the students' potential, which causes dissatisfaction among them, leading them to boycott the pedagogical work, simply by not making an effort to master the technique. This gives the impression that the project was poorly designed and poorly implemented, which is true regarding the second part and, regarding the first, it is also part of the topic, because the teacher must analyze his group with deep experience and submit them to reading tests until identifying which dimension they are in and what can be done, in didactic terms, to meet their demands and raise them to higher levels of learning. It follows that teaching and learning to read is an exhaustive, continuous task that must be verified at every step that is applied to the object.

THE EXPERIENCE OF READING IN THE PROCESS OF INTELLECTUAL FORMATION

Language and reality are closely related in the sense that the former is the means through which the latter can become explicit. When children come into contact with the world, they begin to experiment with different relationships, engaging with different forms of coexistence, with unknown elements, adverse situations and with intricate ways of being and existing in the world as they have experiences. One of these is through reading the world around them, beginning to understand what is related to their actions and reactions. They then come into contact with the written word and develop reading strategies, that is, reading the word, the formal act of decoding graphic signs.

The *reading* of the world is followed by the interpretation of this same world, in which the child is able to situate himself in time and space. He begins to understand why such relationships occur, understanding his process of growth and maturation. In this way, the child is able to come into contact with situations that he was unfamiliar with. He observes situations that he had not experienced before and gains information about the lives of the people around him, the individual history of each of them, how they dress, what behaviors they display, what they do, how they speak and express themselves.

One of the greatest challenges facing schools is to turn their students into good readers. This can be achieved by teachers who have had the experience of reading and interpreted it as positive, and who see reading not only as a means of knowing and understanding the evolution of the world and solving practical problems, but also as a pleasure.

Through their history, individuals observe and seek to understand nature and everything that the known world has to offer. Amidst so many transformations, each acquired knowledge becomes a heritage of humanity, being accumulated and transmitted socially by successive generations throughout history. Therefore, teaching how to read in order to learn must be accompanied by teaching how to read in order to read. It is important to make students aware that reading is also an instrument for entertainment; it is a creative tool that allows them to explore real or imaginary worlds, which brings us closer to other individuals and their ideas, and is capable of converting us into explorers of the intrinsic and extrinsic human universe through imagination, which results in rewriting thought, that is, transforming it.

It should be taken into account that, at different levels of education, there must be time and space scheduled for *reading for the sake of reading* , *reading for pleasure* . For many, school is still a place where reading is assessed and memorized. And, in view of this scenario, it is up to the school to exercise the social function of encouraging and promoting the practice of reading, in order to face with safety, justice, solidarity and reflection the most diverse challenges posed by reality.

Being a reader means having an absolutely infinite path of discovery and understanding of what is beyond the empirical knowledge given. It is essential for the development of a child in development to listen to different stories, readings, poems, nursery rhymes and handle books. These activities, as reading practices, must be present daily in the life of the learner, from infancy until the end of their academic cycles and thus persist throughout their life, so that they develop a taste for reading and, later, use texts autonomously, understanding that, “reading cannot be a secondary activity in the classroom or in life, an activity to which the teacher and the school do not dedicate more than a few miserable minutes. There is a huge disregard for reading, for texts, for the programming of this activity in school” (CAGLIARI, 1990, p. 173).

The role of the school, then, is to allow students to encounter books and develop a taste for reading and develop their literary development. Reading is a continuous learning process that helps to develop and dynamize simple and complex thoughts, as it encourages reflection. It is an inexhaustible source of knowledge that helps students understand the world, fostering inner growth and providing opportunities to experience the most diverse emotions.

To be successful in developing readers, the school's teaching staff must include professionals who are passionate about books, breaking the sense of obligation and converting reading into a spontaneous and stimulating act, triggering pleasurable moments.

The biggest obstacle to teaching reading is precisely the lack of professionals with this profile in the classroom. Most teachers come from an education that does not form them, but

rather *deforms them* ; and thus, they are not prepared to accompany this period of transition in which great contrasts and contradictions are concentrated; in addition, they complain about the lack of appropriate teaching materials to carry out their work safely. However, their knowledge and practice are the most valuable teaching materials they need.

It is not possible to understand, in a simplistic way, the problem of students' reading difficulties, and it is even more complex for the teacher to claim that it is impossible to teach such a task. The issue is that this action cannot be carried out in isolation from the historical and sociological process that encompasses civilizations; because the more one knows about the past, the easier it becomes to understand current facts; however, to hold the past as the only factor responsible for the educational decline that we face in the present is to make a strict statement that one does not know and does not have a formula that could contribute to, at least, minimizing the problem.

CONCLUSION

The acquisition of reading skills should never be considered a problem, but rather a problem. This paradox makes it clear that its discussion, as a present, constant and growing need in a literate world, should always be interpreted as a process in development, given that new potential readers are constantly being inserted into schools and other fields of learning. Through their mastery, there is the opportunity to compare knowledge from various fields and times, mistakes and successes, conflicting situations and expressions of thought from contemporary authors and from other eras.

Learning to read is the first step towards achieving reading proficiency and this should be a careful and well-planned process; because, by demanding fluency in reading and writing from a child, this can create a block in their creative capacity, limited by their mental age and which is not within their reach to meet the expectations set by teachers. It is always important to clarify that learning to read is linked to linguistic maturation, cognitive stage, cerebral maturity, influence of parents and friends, opportunities to access documents, books, magazines and an environment that requires this transformation.

The processes of learning to read and write are essential parts of the school and academic curricula, and what makes didactic and methodological actions concentrated in the early years is the condition of ignorance of linguistic signs in their expressed form. When a child arrives at school to learn to read and write, he or she has already heard an immeasurable range of words; however, as he or she is unaware of the symbolic organization of letters and their union, he or

she ends up repeating the word, without being able to interpret it when he or she finds it represented somewhere. The same will happen when, having already filed away all the letters of the alphabet in his or her memory, the child hears a word that he or she has never seen written; this child will write it according to the sounds he or she understands. Hence the condition of literacy and literacy, in which it is not enough to know how to read and much less to know how to write; mechanisms of high complexity and that require concrete experiences are necessary until it is possible to determine how effective the learning of reading and writing is, through the methodological system adopted for this purpose.

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